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Fostering Academic Excellence: Stakeholder Support in the Implementation of National Learning Camp

Linrose L. Orge, * Jennelyn A. Caya, Grethel F. Desales, Jonamae L. Preglo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assessed the various stakeholders' support for the National Learning Camp (NLC) implementation at Liloan Elementary School in Liloan, Cebu. A qualitative method engaging in a key informant interview using a semi-structured interview guide, purposive sampling in determining the 20 respondents and thematic analysis was utilized in this paper to determine the stakeholder support initiatives in the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024. The findings revealed how the school head, acting as a stakeholder, facilitated positive interactions and connections between parents, students, and teachers while emphasizing their role in the program's implementation. The school head also looked for alternatives for the limited educational resources used during the National Learning Camp's implementation. The teachers were wholly committed to using NLC in lesson planning, mentoring, performance evaluation, and parent communication to guarantee that pupils had mastered literacy and numeracy. As an essential stakeholder, the parents have shown their utmost support by attending several parent-teacher conferences, watching their kid's development, contributing financially, and offering their volunteer time when needed. Despite financial limitations, budgetary restrictions, and instructional time constraints, the National Learning Camp significantly improved the pupils' academic excellence and performance, instilling a sense of optimism in all stakeholders, including the audience, about the potential of the NLC.

Keywords: *academic excellence, implementation, national learning camp, pupils, stakeholder support*

Introduction

Stakeholders are pivotal in shaping and supporting educational efforts in the modern educational landscape. In Indonesia, teachers perceive stakeholder support as primarily informative and instrumental, lacking emotional, social networking, and reward aspects (Nirmala et al., 2019). In the education sector, Panela & Panela (2020) observed that the number of volunteers affects stakeholder support for school programs in the Philippines. By offering pupils more prosperous learning opportunities and extra support outside of the usual classroom setting, the National Learning Camp (NLC) marks a significant attempt to improve educational performance. Gaining support from stakeholders and understanding their needs is essential to the success and long-term viability of the program. Thus, this qualitative study aimed to investigate the support of different stakeholders in the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) as the basis for the development of the National Learning Camp sustainable implementation plan.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the stakeholder support initiatives in implementing the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024 in Liloan Elementary School, Liloan, Cebu, as the basis for developing the National Learning Camp sustainable implementation plan. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What were the in-depth insights into the support provided by school administrators, teachers, and parents in the implementation of the NLC in terms of their:
 - 1.1. roles;
 - 1.2. contributions; and
 - 1.3. perceived outcomes?
2. What were the perceived implications of teachers and students to the stakeholder support on the implementation of the national learning camp in terms of:
 - 2.1. effectiveness; and
 - 2.2. sustainability?
3. What challenges and concerns were observed during the implementation of the National Learning Camp?
4. Based on the findings, what sustainable implementation plan can be developed?

Literature Review

Stakeholder Theory

The emergence of stakeholder theory can attribute to the increasing complexity and dynamism of the organizational environment throughout the 1980s. According to Freeman et al. (2020), this strategy involves strategic management that considers all stakeholders, including consumers, suppliers, owners, employees, and local communities, to generate value for all parties involved. Institutional stakeholders are crucial to the curriculum's implementation, according to Karakuş (2021). Mahajan et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of stakeholder theory in producing diverse advantages for different stakeholders. A stakeholder is any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the institutions' objectives (Freeman et al., 2020). Martín et al. (2021) and Belita et

al. (2020) noted that stakeholder interaction is not just important, but it's a collaborative process for curriculum implementation. Various stakeholder classifications have been put forth. Stakeholders are classified into the following two categories: internal and external. (Jakhar, 2017) Internal stakeholders include students, teachers, and administrators, while external stakeholders include parents, community members, government officials, and policymakers. In order to build mutually advantageous partnerships for the institution, collaborative activities with stakeholders improve curriculum quality, relevance, and opportunities for students' future professional success (Bidandi et al., 2022).

DepEd Order No. 014, series of 2023

This department's order talks about the policy guidelines for implementing the National Learning Camp. The Department of Education has adopted this policy because of its agenda, which is MATATAG: *Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa*. The objective of this policy is to close the achievement disparities and help K–12 students in all public elementary and secondary schools across the country meet academic standards. (Department of Education, 2023) The National Learning Camp has a two-fold purpose: improving the performance of the learner and strengthening the capacity of the teacher. The NLC is structured into three stages, each designed to enhance the learning experience. The learning areas' depth, breadth, and complexity are increased for students attending these enhancement camps. By DepED Order No. 014, s.2023, Consolidation Camp offers additional practice and application on the previously taken competencies.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative method engaging in a key informant interview using a semi-structured interview guide and thematic analysis was utilized in this paper to determine the stakeholder support initiatives in the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024.

Participants

A purposive sampling technique was employed to determine the respondents of the study with a total number of 20, consisting of nine (9) teachers handling NLC in Grade 1-3, ten (10) parents, and School Head as stakeholders of Liloan Elementary School, Liloan, Cebu.

Instrument

For a qualitative study, the researcher herself was the main instrument for data collection. The researcher observed, took down notes, and conducted the interview. Additionally, the researcher used a semi-structured interview guide validated by experts. The researcher asked questions about the identified stakeholders' experiences to set the stakeholder respondents mood, their perception of their role, contributions and outcomes of the NLC implementation. They were also asked of their observed and experienced challenges during the NLC Implementation. The researcher practiced extreme caution by using open-ended questions.

Procedure

To facilitate the study, the researcher first asked permission from the School Head of Liloan Elementary School to conduct the study. Upon approval, the researchers then administer the scheduled semi-structured interview with the respondents. First, the researcher presented the consent form to the participants and let them freely sign the agreement. Then, the Key Informant Interview was conducted and recorded. After collecting the participant responses, the data was transcribed and evaluated most accurately by obtaining in-depth insights into stakeholder support in NLC 2024. The stakeholder respondents are interviewed according to their preferred schedule, time, and venue.

Ethical Considerations

Before the interview took place, the researchers obtained permission from the respondents by asking for their permission to participate in this research study with their full consent. Respondents were properly notified of their rights during the interview process. Human privacy has been employed during the interview process and data collection. The researchers protected the secrecy of the responses and the respondents' identities. Finally, the researchers assured that all research materials would be destroyed following the completion of the study.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the outcome of the qualitative analysis of the research questions' answers. The results are presented based on the emergent themes, sub-themes, core ideas, and categorization.

School head as a Stakeholder of NLC

Role and Contribution

School heads, also known as principals or headteachers, play a crucial role in the administration and leadership of schools. Their responsibilities encompass various aspects that contribute to the overall functioning and success of the implementation of the National Learning Camp as a school program. The school head of Liloan Central School served as an implementer of the program from the

planning, orientation, preparation, implementation, and evaluation phases. As stated, *“The National Learning Camp Implementation needs to undergo a careful planning, thorough communication with teachers and parents in the process ensuring oneness in the success of the NLC Implementation”*. According to Llarena (2023), Philippines school principals play a key role in implementing programs through technical assistance, mentoring, and leading planning and implementation. It is the head's role to monitor the right and appropriate procedure in the success and conduct of the National Learning Camp. As a stakeholder, the school head provides a healthy interaction and connection between the parents, students, and teachers, highlighting their importance in the implementation of the program. The principal said that *“We have to establish open communication and let our parents feel that they are an essential part of this program. If we care for them, it will manifest through their support”*. The Key Informant School head had found ways to provide alternatives for the limited learning resources in implementing the National Learning Camp. *“Limited resources has been a so long challenge faced by our school, but we intend to find support and help from different individuals and stakeholders to provide the pupil’s needs”*. Support, collaboration, and encouragement of teachers to do their best for the students to learn were seen as valuable strategies to invigorate the teachers and encourage them to persevere in the conduct of NLC.

Perceived Outcome

The Key Informant School head believed that implementing the National Learning Camp was worthwhile as it was evident that the program greatly enhanced the students' academic excellence. Students have shown mastery of the different competencies taught and has increased their performances. *“It is worthwhile witnessing the progress of our learners specially in literacy and numeracy”*. The teachers have also benefited from implementing the NLC as the experience enhanced their teacher effectiveness. Overall, the teachers and students have increased their capacity and knowledge in every subject area.

Teachers as a Stakeholder of NLC

Role and Contribution

All the teacher respondents showed full dedication in implementing NLC to plan lessons, guide students, assess performance, and communicate with parents. When asked about their contributions, most teachers perceived themselves as very significant in the conduct of NLC. *“Though NLC has been an additional job to do, we are teachers, we will follow what is ought to be done. Also, this NLC will give us time to assist our pupils to improve their level of competency. Their improvement compensates the effort we exerted for them to learn”*. This means that their contributions highlighted their total commitment to enhancing the literacy and numeracy skills of the learners. When it comes to putting educational policies and innovations into practice, teachers are essential. (Katshuna & Shikalepo, 2023).

Perceived Outcome

The teachers' views on the National Learning Camp are significantly positive. The teacher respondents strongly agreed that the camp effectively promotes excellence. They further emphasized that students showed increased engagement and motivation in enhancing literacy and numeracy because of the camp. The teachers reported a very positive influence on academic performance and learners' participation in the camp. *Our students specially those with grades in developing have become satisfactory, the shy one’s learned to slowly speak up. These small and positive improvements are evident during the NLC*. All teachers have noted significant gains in the learners' literacy and numeracy abilities, self-assurance, and fundamental fine motor skills. The camp offers long-term advantages by enhancing learners' learning experiences and critical competencies. When teachers foster a healthy environment and sense of well-being among themselves, pupils may do better academically and advance in their social and emotional development even outside of the classroom (Saro et al., 2023).

Parents as a Stakeholder of NLC

Role and Contribution

Parents play a vital role in the success of every endeavor, especially in the sustainability of different programs in the Department of Education. Parents mostly 30-40 years old of the elementary students participating in the National Learning Camp (NLC) have shown moderate involvement in implementing the National Learning Camp. Most of the parents are working as a vendor to support their children in their education. *I really tried my very best to provide and allocate money for the needs of my child during the NLC. From the transportation, to snacks, foods and other learning materials. Though I only have a small income, I budget certain amount for my child’s needs.* Parents in the Philippines know their crucial role in their children's education but face challenges like poverty and low educational attainment that limit their involvement (Joemar and Mayeth, 2023). *“It brings me joy to see my child enjoying school, education is the only legacy I can give to them”*. As parents, it has been found that despite their situation, they knew their role in encouraging their children to attend the NLC. Additionally, parents have given their all-out support by participating in different parent-teacher meetings and monitoring their children's progress.

However, the results showed that parents can sometimes assist their children in their homework and learning activities. *“I can’t find time to assist my child in the homework and learning activities because I have a lot of household chores to attend to”*. Despite this, parents have extended their support for the success of the NLC Implementation, their financial support, and sparing their volunteer time whenever necessary.

Perceived Outcome

In every endeavor of the projects conducted, outcomes form a highlight of the success of its implementation. The parents perceived the National Learning Camp (NLC) Implementation as successful and have met the parents' expectations in fostering academic excellence in their children. They also believed that the NLC has helped a lot in improving the students' grades, for it enhances the student's motivation and interest in learning. "*NLC is better because they can learn something while they are at school rather than enjoying vacation playing and watching TV all day*". Moreover, the NLC has enhanced their children's social skills and personality, leading to better study habits

Challenges and Suggestions

One of the challenges faced by the school heads in the implementation was the limited availability of resources and time constraints. In the conduct of classes, it has been observed that the given time still needed to be more to finish the assigned task/activity for the day. "*Tasks are planned according to time allocation but in the actual setting, you have to adjust to the level of responses of each student and find ways to make it easier for them to grasp the lesson. It really takes time.*" As school heads, teachers have been reminded to be time-conscious and to design activities within the allocated time frame. Limited resources had long been an issue of every school. Thus, the school head found initiatives to seek additional funding and resources to cope with it. Principals need help in financial management, including policy-related procedures, budget allocation issues, and limited training opportunities (Gaspar et al., 2022). Stakeholders have also been tapped for the assistance they can offer the schools. However, despite the encouraging responses, the teachers have several difficulties, such as a shortage of supplies, scheduling conflicts, inadequate training, and low parental involvement. As much as parents tried their best to provide their children with their needs during NLC, results showed that financial limitations are still a prevailing challenge. Parents have also suggested that teachers provide more engaging activities to keep the student's attention during the training. "*My child always talks how fun is their activity at school, I hope all teachers are providing learning activities for them to enjoy*". Time allocation for the said designed activities should also be considered.

Perceived Implication of Stakeholder's Support

Effectiveness

The teachers well received the National Learning Camp. The teachers have collectively agreed that the National Learning Camp (NLC) effectively promotes excellence among learners. Generally speaking, the teacher volunteers' experiences at the National Learning Camp were enjoyable and fulfilling. In the subject of learning, professionals, and students collaborate socially to enhance learning possibilities for both professional and personal development. (King, Steve & McClatchey, Irene & Channer, Bianca. 2022) The National Learning Camp positively affected students' learning results across different aspects. While there is agreement on effectiveness in certain areas, various opinions have arisen regarding the degree of enhancement, particularly in critical thinking abilities.

Stakeholder support, particularly from parents, is crucial to the effectiveness of the National Learning Camp (NLC). The support shown by the parents to their child in joining the National Learning Camp (NLC) relates to the program's outcome. The program can only stand and function what it needs to do with the parents' share. The relationship between parents and children significantly impacts children's learning results. (Novia et al., 2020) When parents are actively engaged and provide resources and feedback, students are more likely to stay motivated and achieve better learning outcomes, enhancing the program's effectiveness. Parental involvement in their child's education significantly influences numerous beneficial student outcomes. (Garbacz et al., 2022).

Sustainability

Teachers who see the learning camp as helpful may be more likely to endorse it actively, resulting in increased support and favorable stakeholder feedback. Their excitement can assist in garnering more support from parents and the community. The National Learning Camp (NLC) will indeed sustain with this support from the internal and external stakeholders. The implementation of curriculum in the classroom is a key operational responsibility of teachers, and the quality of curriculum implementation will suffer in the absence of teachers' coordinated efforts. (Katshuna & Shikalepo, 2023). However, financial limitations present a long-term challenge to sustaining the National Learning Camp (NLC). Continued collaboration among parents, local organizations, and government bodies is essential to overcoming these challenges and ensuring the program's success and sustainability. Active stakeholder involvement is vital to the program's immediate effectiveness and long-term viability. The engagement of organizations with their surrounding context, which includes stakeholders, is a crucial aspect of sustainable business models. (Velter et al., 2020)

Conclusions

In general, the National Learning Camp (NLC) positively affects teachers' and learners' teaching and learning performance. Improving teachers' training and readily available resources is a highly needed proposal for improvements, as this will promote a more encouraging and practical learning environment to elevate its impact on learners further. To ensure its effectiveness and long-term use, DepEd must address the challenges proactively. Nevertheless, the NLC program supported the continuous improvement of pupils' pursuit of excellence in both numeracy and literacy skills, expanding the program to fit the diverse needs of learners best and highlighting the importance of stakeholder support in fostering a high implementation success rate.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Linrose L. Orge

Cebu Technological University – Philippines

Jennelyn A. Caya

Liloan Central School
Department of Education – Philippines

Grethel F. Desales

City of Naga Division
Department of Education – Philippines

Jonamae L. Preglo

Mandaue City Division
Department of Education – Philippines